

Formulation, development and characterization of Vildagliptin ethosome formulation.

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Abstract:

The objective of current study was to prepare and optimize the ethosomal drug delivery system for Vildagliptin (VLD) to improve the efficacy, sustain release of the drugs and superior patient consent. Ethosomes were prepared by Prepared by cold method using ethanol. Lecithin and cholesterol in different concentration. ethosomes were evaluated for vesicle size, polydispersity index, zeta potential, entrapment efficiency and surface morphology. The in vitro permeability studies were done using franz diffusion cell using cellophane membrane. The vesicle size of all the formulation ranges from 115.1 ± 1.5278 nm to 686.3 ± 3.4521 nm. The smallest vesicle size (115.1 ± 1.5278 nm) was present in VF6 formulation with composition 35% ethanol, 2.5% soya lecithin and 2% cholesterol. The entrapment efficiency of VF6 formulation was found to be highest i.e 74 ± 2.432 % and it ranges from 40 ± 1.361 % to 74 ± 2.432 %. SEM analysis of the optimized VF6 shows that the vesicle are uniform in shape and size with homogeneous dispersion as can be seen from polydispersity index value of 0.230 ± 0.011 . Formulation VF6 showed 6 fold higher ($p < 0.05$) transdermal flux (52.82 ± 2.51 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2/\text{hr}$) than the drug solution (6.01 ± 0.811 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2/\text{hr}$) and 4 fold higher than VF1 formulation (11.27 ± 1.633 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2/\text{hr}$). VF6 ethosomal formulation is considered as the best formulation from vesicle size distribution, polydispersity index, zeta potential, drug entrapment efficiency and in vitro permeation study results.

Keys Works: Ethosome, zeta potential, SEM, in vitro, polydispersity index.

Introduction:

Delivery of drugs via skin is an old concept, as reported in 16th century in which the pod of castor bean plant in water was set on an aching head. These days the transdermal drug delivery is most trusted system for delivering drug to systemic circulation¹. TDDSs represent a noninvasive mean to avoid exposure to the first-pass metabolism and can sustain plasma levels within the therapeutic window over extended periods.² The use of lipid vesicles as drug delivery systems for treatment has attracted increasing attention in recent years.³ However, it is basically believe that conventional liposomes are of little value for this purpose. Liposomes remain confined to the surface of stratum corneum (SC) and, hence, are suitable for topical drug delivery.⁵ only specially designed vesicles were shown to deliver drugs across the skin layers.⁶ Drug encapsulated in lipid vesicles prepared

from phospholipids and nonionic surfactant serves as nontoxic penetration enhancer for drugs due to its amphiphilic nature. Lipid rich vesicles like liposome and niosomes can be used for encapsulation hydrophilic and lipophilic as well as low and high molecular weight drugs^{7,8} However these lipid rich vesicles has a problem of poor skin permeability. Introduction of ethosomes, another novel lipid carrier developed by Touitou et al has shown enhanced skin permeation as compared to conventional liposomes^{2,9}

Ethosomal systems were found to be significantly superior at delivering drugs through the skin in terms of both quantity and depth that are capable of delivering various chemical applications¹⁰.

Diabetes mellitus is a chronic metabolic disorder characterized by high blood glucose concentration hyperglycemia caused by insulin deficiency, often combined with insulin resistance¹¹. VLD an oral hypoglycemic agent commonly uses in treatment of Non-Insulin Dependent Diabetes Mellitus (NIDDM) on oral administration is associated with several side effects like hypoglycemia, frequent GI side effects such as nausea, vomiting, heartburn, anorexia, increased appetite etc. Since these drugs are usually intended to be taken for a long period, patient compliance is also very important, hence the objective of present study involve formulation of ethosomal gel using soya lecithin as vehicle forming agent, ethanol, propylene glycol and cholesterol¹² In the present study ethosomes with different concentration of phospholipids and ethanol were prepared and evaluated for particle size, polydispersity index (PDI), zeta potential, extrudability and entrapment efficiency (EE) then a chosen formula was incorporated into a gel dosage form to investigate the potential application of ethosomal gel for transdermal delivery of VLD a anti diabetic drug.

Materials and Methods:

Methods:

Preparation of ethosomes¹³

Ethosomes was prepared by cold method. VLD was dissolved in varying concentrations of ethanol and water in desired quantity, with 10 ml of propylene glycol by keeping the concentration of soya lecithin. Required amount of ethanolic mixture was taken individually and heated at 30 °C on a water bath; water was steadily added to the above blend drop wise in the centre of the vessel. The resulting blend was stirred at 700 rpm for 10 minutes to get the ethosomal vesicles. Ethosomes

thus obtained were subjected to sonication at 4⁰C and stirring at 700 rpm for 15 minutes (3 cycles at interval of 5 minutes). The constitution of all the formulations is shown in table 1.

Vesicles size, polydispersity index (PI) and zeta potential^{14,15}

Vesicle size and zeta potential were determined by dynamic light scattering method (DLS), using a computerized inspection system (Malvern Zetamaster, ZEM 5002, Malvern, UK). The measurement was done in triplicates. The polydispersity index (PI) was used as a measurement of the particle size homogeneity for the prepared ethosomal formulations. Polydispersity index (PI) less than 0.4 indicates a homogenous and monodisperse population.

Percentage entrapment efficiency (EE)^{16,17}

The entrapment capacity of ethosomal vesicles was determined by ultracentrifugation method. The drug containing ethosomal formulations were kept overnight at 4 °C and centrifuged in ultracentrifuge (Tarsons) at 12000 rpm for 30 min. The sediment and supernatant was removed and drug amount was determined by using UV-Visible spectrophotometer in both the sediment and the supernatant. The entrapment capacity was calculated by using following equation,

$$[(T-S) / T] * 100$$

Where, *T* is the total amount of drug that is detected both in the supernatant and sediment, and *S* is the amount of drug found in the supernatant.

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)^{18,19}

The morphology and structure of selected ethosomal formulation was determined by the Scanning Electron Microscopy. A drop of the sample was placed on a carbon-coated copper grid to leave a thin film. Before the film dried on the grid, it was stained with 1% phosphotungstic acid. A drop of the staining solution was added on the film and the excess of the solution was drained off with a filter paper. The grid was allowed to air dry thoroughly, and samples were viewed in a SEM.

In vitro skin permeability study:^{20,21,21,23}

For the in vitro permeability study, excised rat skin pre shaved carefully and the abdominal skin separated from the underlying connective tissue with the scalpel, the excised skin was then placed on aluminum foil and the dermal side of the skin was gently teased off for any adhering fat or subcutaneous tissue. Prepared skin was then mounted on franz diffusion cell (area, 3.14 cm²) and the test formulation was applied on the epidermal side of the skin. 1 ml sample was withdrawn from the receptor compartment containing 25 ml of the phosphate buffer pH 7.4 maintained at

37°C ± 1°C, at appropriate time intervals and analyzed spectrophotometrically at 210 nm to determine the cumulative amount of drug permeated across the skin in the receptor medium irrespective of the drug deposited in the skin layers. An equal volume of fresh phosphate buffer pH 7.4 was replaced after each sampling into the compartment. The study was performed in triplicate and average values were calculated. The percent cumulative amount of drug permeated across the skin per square surface area was evaluated and plotted against time to calculate the flux

Result and Discussion:

The composition of various VLD loaded ethosomes developed is shown in the following table 1.

Table 1: Composition of VLD ethosome

Formulation Code	% Drug	% Soya Lecithin	% Cholesterol	% Ethanol	% Propylene glycol	Distilled Water
VF1	1	1.5	2	30	10	Q.S.
VF2	1	1.5	1.5	35	10	Q.S.
VF3	1	2.0	2	30	10	Q.S.
VF4	1	2.0	1.5	35	10	Q.S.
VF5	1	2.5	1.5	30	10	Q.S.
VF6	1	2.5	2	35	10	Q.S.

Characterization of VLD ethosomes

Vesicle size, polydispersity Index, zeta potential and % entrapment efficiency

The outcomes of these parameters are manifested in the following table 2.

Table 2: Characterization of VLD loaded ethosomal formulations

Formulation Code	Vesicle Size (nm)	Polydispersity Index (PI)	% Entrapment efficiency	Zeta Potential (mV)	Flux ($\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2/\text{hr}$)	Permeability Coefficient (cm/hr)
VF1	686.3 \pm 3.4521	0.530 \pm 0.042	59 \pm 2.451	-21.6	11.27 \pm 1.633	0.00714
VF2	318.2 \pm 1.5438	0.642 \pm 0.027	68 \pm 2.539	-23.5	17.60 \pm 1.54	0.01120
VF3	129.3 \pm 1.1531	0.352 \pm 0.025	45 \pm 1.250	-18.1	26.54 \pm 1.61	0.01851
VF4	138.3 \pm 1.1817	0.302 \pm 0.010	72 \pm 1.142	-16.8	27.14 \pm 1.26	0.01731
VF5	250.5 \pm 1.1254	0.381 \pm 0.120	40 \pm 1.361	-17.6	24.15 \pm 1.53	0.01528
VF6	115.1 \pm 1.5278	0.310 \pm 0.011	74 \pm 2.432	-16.4	52.82 \pm 2.51	0.02385
Drug Solution	--	---	---	---	6.01 \pm 0.811	0.03269

Values indicates mean \pm SD, Where n = 3

Ethosome formulations were evaluated for vesicle size, polydispersity index, zeta potential and % entrapment efficiency. The vesicle mean diameters for all formulations are shown in table 2. The result shows narrow peak for all formulations, which indicating that the size of vesicle population is comparatively uniform. In accordance with other researcher, this decrease in the mean diameter of the vesicle is due to the presence of ethanol as it confers negative charge to the system causing reduction in size of vesicle²⁴. Higher concentration of ethanol produced smaller vesicle size. Ethanol confers a surface negative net charge to the ethosome which causes the size of vesicles to decrease probably due to interpenetrating of hydrocarbon chain. The size of ethosomal vesicles increase with decreasing ethanol concentration²⁵.

It was observed that the vesicles of composite ethosomal formulations (VF1 – VF6) varied in size range of 686.3 ± 3.4521 nm to 115.1 ± 1.5278 nm. Polydispersity index was determined as a measure of homogeneity in formulation. Polydispersity index indicate homogeneous population of ethosome vesicle in formulation, it was found to be 0.02385 for VF6 formulation.

Drug loading and % entrapment efficiency are key parameters that evaluate the delivery potentiality of a system. The % entrapment efficiency of various ethosome formulations is shown in table 2. Amounts of ethanol and lecithin used for ethosome preparation were found to have influenced the entrapment efficiency. Increasing the concentration of ethanol shows increase in entrapment efficiency, which may be due increase in fluidity of the membrane²⁶. (The effect of ethanol concentration on vesicle size and entrapment efficiency was investigated by Touito *et al*)²⁷, % entrapment efficiency of ethosome formulation was found in the range of 74 ± 2.432 % to 40 ± 1.361 % highest for VF6 formulation.

Based on the above results, formulation VF6 (2.5% soya lecithin, 2% cholesterol, 35% ethanol and 10% propylene glycol) was found to have acceptable characteristics features and considered as optimized.

Figure 01: Zeta potential analysis of ethosomal formulation

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

The results of transmission electron microscopy showed that the prepared ethosome formulations are uniform in size and spherical in shape. From the SEM results it can be concluded that the drug has been successfully encapsulate. (Figure 02)

Figure 02: Scanning electron microscopy image of ethosomal VF6 formulation

In vitro skin permeability study:

In vitro skin permeation study for ethosomal formulation was performed for 7 hours using excised rat skin and compared with ethanolic solution of drug. Transdermal flux for different ethosomal formulation ranged between 11.27 ± 1.633 to $52.82 \pm 2.51 \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2/\text{hr}$ (table 4). Flux for VF6 formulation (2.5% lecithin, 35% ethanol and 2 % cholesterol) was 4 fold higher than that of VF1 formulation ($11.27 \pm 1.633 \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2/\text{hr}$) and 7 fold higher than that of the ethanolic solution of drug ($6.01 \pm 0.811 \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2/\text{hr}$). This may be due to the small vesicle size, high entrapment efficiency and high concentration of ethanol resulting in fluidization of stratum corneum layer, thus reducing its barrier property. Also propylene glycol in the formulations serves as penetration enhancer.

VF6 formulation is considered as the best and optimized formulation from vesicle size distribution, polydispersity index, zeta potential, drug entrapment efficiency and *in vitro* permeation study results.

Figure 3: In vitro drug release study of various ethosomal formulations.

Conclusion:

Ethosomes loaded with VLD was prepared by varying the concentration of soya lecithin and ethanol. The prepared ethosomal formulation was characterized for zeta potential, Polydispersity Index (PI), entrapment efficiency and in vitro permeability studies. It was observed that ethosomal formulation show better permeability and stability with enhanced bioavaibility enhanced permeability may be attributed to the high alcohol concentration in ethosomes thus acting as a permeation enhancer. Thus it can be concluded that the prepared ethosomal formulation loaded with VLD is safe with great potential and effective transdermal drug delivery system. Further the research should be done to sustain or control the release of drug from ethosome to archive prolong action and better patient compliance.

References:

1. Nida A, Kamla P. Cavamax W7 composite ethosomal gel of clotrimazole for improved topical delivery: Development and Comparison with Ethosomal Gel. **AAPS Pharm Sci Tech.**, 2012, 13 (1), 344–355.
2. Jamakandi V.G, Mulla J.S, Vinay B.L, Formulation, characterization and evaluation of matrix type transdermal patches of a model antihypertensive drug, **Asian J. Pharm.**, 1, 2009, PP 59-65.
3. Bagyalakshmi J, Vmshikrishna R. P, Formulation, development and in vitro and in vivo evaluation of membrane-moderated transdermal systems of ampicillin sodium in ethanol: pH 4.7 buffer solvent system, **AAPS Pharm. Sci. Tech.**, 8(1), 2008, PP E50-E55.
4. Murthy T.E.G.K, Ramana R.V, Kishore B.M, Influence of polymers on the release of Carvediol from transdermal films, **Indian Drugs.**, 45(12), 2008, PP 970-974.
5. Yang Y, Manda P, Pavurala N, Khan MA, Krishnaiah YSR. Development and validation of in vitro in vivo correlation (IVIVC) for estradiol transdermal drug delivery systems. **J Control Release.** 2015; 210:58-66.

6. Subheet J, Ashok K. T, Bharti S, Narendra K. J. Formulation and Evaluation of Ethosomes for Transdermal Delivery of Lamivudine. **AAPS Pharm. Sci. Tech.**, 8(4), 2007, E1 – E9.
7. Schreier H, Bouwstra J. Liposomes and niosomes as a drug carriers: dermal and transdermal drug delivery. **J Control Release**. 1994; 30:1 to 15.
8. Touitou E, Dayan N, Bergelson L, Godin B, Eliaz M. Ethosomes novel vesicular carriers for enhanced delivery: characterization and skin penetration properties. **J Control Release**. 2000; 65:403 - 418.
9. Heeremans J.L.M, Gerristen H.R, Meusen S.P, Mijuheer F.W, Panday G.R.S, Prevost R, Kluft C, Crommelin D.J.A, The preparation of tissue-type plasminogen activator (t-PA) containing liposomes: Entrapment efficiency and ultracentrifugation damage. **J Drug Target.**, 1995, 3, PP 301-310.
10. Sujitha B, Krishnamoorthy B, Muthukumaran M, Formulation and evaluation of piroxicam loaded ethosomal gel for transdermal delivery, **Int J Adv Pharma Genuine Res.**, 2014, 2 (1), PP 34–35.
11. Dheeraj T.B, Yogesh Kumar A.B, Kapil R.B, Venkatesh B.P, Mangesh K.S, Dinesh K.J, *in - vitro* and *in - vivo* evaluation of diclofenac sodium gel prepared with cellulose ether and carbopol 934P, **Trop J Pharm Res.**, 2013, 12 (4), PP 489–494.
12. Pavan K. Chintala, Padmapreetha J, Formulation And *In-Vitro* Evaluation Of Gel Containing Ethosomes Entrapped With Etodolac, **Int J Pharma Sci Res.**, 2014, 5 (2), PP 630-635.
13. Kshirsagar R.V, Vikas J, Wattamwar S, Effect of different viscosity grade HPMC polymers on gastroretantive drug delivery of Metformin Hcl, **Int J App Pharm.**, 2009, 1 (1), PP 44-50.

14. Atul K.G, Lalit M. N, Meenakshi C, Effect of different viscosity grade HPMC polymers on gastroretentive drug delivery of metformin HCl, **Int J App Pharm.**, 1 (1), 2009, PP 44-50.
15. Yi-Ping F, Yi-Hung T, Pao-chu W, Yaw – Bin H, Comparison of 5- aminolevulinic acid – encapsulated liposome versus ethosome for skin delivery for photodynamic therapy, **Int J Pharm.**, 356, 2008, PP 144– 152.
16. Banga A. K, Chein Y.W, Hydrogel – based iontotherapeutic delivery devices for transdermal delivery of peptide/protein drugs, **Pharm Res.**, 10, 1993, PP 697–702.
17. Godin B, Touitou E, Rubinstein F, Athamna A, Athamna M, A new approach for treatment of deep skin infections by an ethosomal antibiotic preparation: An *in vivo* study, **J Antimicrob Chemother.**, 55 (6), 2005, PP 989–994.
18. Subject J, Ashok K.T, Bharti S, Narendra K.J, Formulation and evaluation of ethosomes for transdermal delivery of lamivudine, **APPS Pharm Sci Tech.**, 8 (4), 2007, PP E1–E9.
19. Maghraby G.M.M, Williams A.C, Barry B.W, Oestradiol skin delivery from ultra-deformable liposomes: Refinement of surfactant concentration, **Int J Pharm.**, 196 (1), 2000, PP 63–74.
20. Donatella P, Giuseppe L, Domenico M, Franco A, Massimo F, Ethosomes for skin delivery of ammonium glycyrrhizinate permeation through human skin and *in- vivo* anti-inflammatory activity on human volunteers, **J Controlled Release.**, 106, 2005, PP 99–110.
21. Fry D.W, White J.C, Goldman I. D, Rapid separation of low molecular weight solutes from liposomes without dilution, **Anal Biochem.**, 90, 1978, PP 809–815.

22. Torchilin V.P, Weissig V, Liposomes a practical approach, (2nd edition), Oxford University Press, Oxford, 2003, PP 36–39.
23. Cevc G, Schatzlein A, Blume G, Transdermal drug carriers: Basic properties, optimization and transfer efficiency in case of epicutaneously applied peptides, **J Controlled Release.**, 36, 1995, PP 3–16.
24. Pandya Narendra, Patel Manvi, Bhaskar V.H., Patel K.R. Development of Transdermal Drug Delivery system of A model Antidiabetic Agent. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Science and Bioscientific Research.* 2011: 1 (1): 59 – 64.
25. Verma D.D, Fahr A. Synergistic penetration effect of ethanol and phospholipids on the topical delivery of cyclosporine A, **J Control Release.**, 97 (1), 2004, PP55–66.
26. Guo J, Ping Q, Sun G, Jiao C, Lecithin vesicular carriers for transdermal delivery of cyclosporine A, **Int J Pharm.**, 194 (2), 2000, PP 201–207.
27. Barry B.W, Is Transdermal drug delivery research still important today, **Drug Discov Today.**, 6 (19), 2001, PP 967– 971.